

BIT ERROR RATE ANALYSIS OF SM-MIMO AND SSP-SM-MIMO

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Abstract:

The ever increasing demand for higher data rates in wireless communication systems requires innovative transmission schemes achieving a high spectral efficiency. However, in massive SM-MIMO, the optimal maximum likelihood detector has the high complexity, while state-of-the-art low-complexity detectors for small-scale SM-MIMO suffer from an obvious performance loss., by exploiting the structured sparsity of multiple SM signals, a low complexity signal detector was proposed based on structured compressive sensing to improve the signal detection performance. Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) low complexity receiver which utilizes the compressive sensing detection for Spatial Modulation in large scale MIMO system in order to reduce the system complexity. In conventional MIMO system, huge amount of antennas is used at both ends to exploit the multipath propagation. This system maximizes the throughput performance and data rates are increased but only at the cost of high hardware complexity and increased power-consumption. Moreover we analyzed the technique using high level modulations (i.e. M-PSK for different values of M). Detection algorithms used are Zero-Forcing and Minimum mean square estimator. Performance is analyzed in terms of BER (bit error rate) vs. SNR (signal to noise ratio).

Introduction:

Multiple antenna systems (MIMO) attract significant attention due to their ability of resolving the bottleneck of traffic capacity in wireless networks. The idea behind MIMO is that the signals on the transmitting (Tx) antennas and the receiving (Rx) antennas are combined in such a way that the quality (bit-error rate or BER) or the data rate (bits/sec) of the communication for each MIMO user will be improved. Such an advantage can be to increase the network's quality of service. Spatial modulation (SM)-MIMO exploits the pattern of one or several simultaneously active antennas out of all available transmit antennas to transmit extra information. Compared with small-scale SM-MIMO which only introduces the limited gain in spectrum efficiency, massive SM-MIMO is recently proposed by integrating SM-MIMO with massive MIMO working at 3~6 GHz to achieve higher spectrum efficiency. In massive SM-MIMO systems, the base station (BS) uses a large number of low-cost antennas for higher spectrum efficiency but only one or several power-hungry transmit radio frequency (RF) chains for power saving, while the user can compactly employ the multiple receive diversity antennas with low correlation. Since the power consumption and hardware cost are largely dependent on the number of simultaneously active transmit RF chains (especially the power amplifier), massive-MIMO is efficiency, reduced power consumption, lower hardware cost, etc. For massive SM-MIMO, due to the small number of receive antennas at the user and massive antennas at the BS, the signal detection is a challenging large-scale underdetermined problem. When the number of transmit antennas becomes large, the optimal maximum likelihood (ML) signal detector suffers from the prohibitively high complexity. Low-complexity signal vector (SV)-based detector has been proposed for SM-MIMO, but it is confined to SM-MIMO with single transmit RF chain. The SM is generalized, where more than one active antennas are used to transmit independent signal constellation symbols for spatial multiplexing. Linear minimum mean square error (LMMSE)-based signal detector and sphere decoding (SD)-based detector can be used for SM-MIMO systems with multiple transmit RF chains. But they are only suitable for well or over determined SM-MIMO with $N_t \geq N_r$, and suffer from a significant performance loss in underdetermined SM-MIMO systems with $N_t < N_r$, where N_t and N_r are the numbers of transmit and receive antennas, respectively. Due to limited number of RF chains, SM signals have the inherent sparsity, which can be considered by exploiting the compressive sensing (CS) theory for improved signal detection performance. By far, CS has been widely used in wireless communications and the CS-based signal detectors have been proposed for underdetermined small-scale SM-MIMO. However, their bit-error-rate (BER) performance still has a significant gap compared with that of the optimal ML detector, especially in massive SM-MIMO with large N_t , N_r , and $N_r \ll N_t$. In SM-MIMO systems, the transmitter has N_t transmit antennas but $N_a < N_t$ transmit RF chains, and the receiver has N_r receive antennas. Each SM signal consists of two symbols: the spatial constellation symbol obtained by mapping bits to a pattern of N_a active antennas out of N_t transmit antennas, and N_a independent signal constellation symbols coming from the M-ary signal constellation set (e.g., QAM). At the receiver, the received signal $y \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times 1}$ can be expressed as $y = Hx + w$, where $x \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times 1}$ is the SM signal transmitted by the transmitter, $w \in \mathbb{C}^{N_r \times 1}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) vector with independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) entries following the circular

symmetric complex Gaussian distribution is the correlated Rayleigh-fading MIMO channel, entries of \tilde{H} are subjected to the i.i.d. distribution $CN(0; 1)$, R_r and R_t are the receiver and transmitter correlation matrices, respectively [13]. The correlation matrix R is given by $r_{ij} = r^{|i-j|}$, where r_{ij} is the i th row and j th column element of R , and r is the correlation coefficient of neighboring antennas. It should be pointed out that H should be known by the receiver and can be acquired by channel estimation. To achieve both high spectrum efficiency and energy efficiency, massive SM-MIMO, which employs massive low-cost antennas but few power-hungry transmit RF chains at the BS to serve the user with comparatively small number of receive antennas, is recently proposed. Existing CS-based signal detectors utilize one received signal vector to recover one sparse SM signal vector, which is a typical single measurement vector (SMV) problem, i.e., $y = Hx + w$. If multiple sparse signals share the common support set and identical measurement matrix, i.e., the reconstruction of $x(t)$'s from $y(t)$'s for $1 \leq t \leq G$ can be considered as the multiple measurement vectors (MMV) problem in SCS theory. The SCS theory has proven that with the same size of the measurement vector, the recovery performance of SCS algorithms is superior to that of conventional CS algorithms. This implies that with the same number of receive antennas N_r , the proposed SCS-based signal detector can outperform conventional CS-based signal detectors.

SCS Based Signal Detector:

This paper proposes a near-optimal structured compressive sensing (SCS)-based signal detector with low complexity for massive SM-MIMO. Structured subspace pursuit (SSP) algorithm at the user to detect multiple SM signals, whereby their structured sparsity is leveraged for improve signal detection performance. Moreover, the SM signal interleaving is proposed to permute SM signals in the same transmission group, so that the channel diversity can be exploited. Theoretical analysis and simulation results verify that the proposed SCS-based signal detector outperforms existing CS-based signal detector. Compared with the conventional MMV problem, our formulated problem is to solve multiple sparse signals with the common support set but having different measurement matrices. Hence both conventional SMV problem and MMV problem can be considered as the special cases of our problem. If $\Pi^{(t)}$'s are identical, becomes the conventional MMV problem, and furthermore if $G = 1$, it reduces to the SMV problem. Therefore, our formulated problem can regarded as a generalized MMV (GMMV) problem.

Proposed Signal Detector:

In SM-MIMO systems, the transmitter has N_t transmit antennas. In transmitter data has applied to the modulation, after modulation interleaving has to be done. After spatial modulation data send to the mimo channel. In receiver reverse operation of transmitter implemented and data to be recovered.

- ✓ At the transmitter: Grouped transmission and interleaving
- ✓ At the receiver: SCS based signal detector

Grouped Transmission and Interleaving at the Transmitter:

We assume that signal constellation symbols in the proposed scheme are mutually independent. Moreover, for the proposed grouped transmission scheme, every G consecutive SM signals are considered as a group, and SM signals in the same transmission group share the same spatial constellation symbol, Due to the conveyed common spatial constellation symbol, in the same transmission group share the same support set and thus have the structured sparsity. It is clear that to introduce such structured sparsity, the effective information bits carried by spatial constellation symbols will be reduced. However as will be demonstrated in our simulations, such structured sparsity allows more reliable signal detection performance and eventually could even improve the BER performance of the whole system without the reduction of the total bit per channel use (bpcu). On the other hand, due to the temporal channel correlation, channels in several consecutive time slots can be considered to be quasistatic, where is the channel associated with the t th SM signal in the group. This implies that if channels used for SM fall into the deep fading, such deep fading usually remains unchanged during G time slots, and the corresponding signal detection performance will be poor. To solve this issue, we

further propose the SM signal interleaving at the transmitter. Specifically, after the original SM signal $x^{(t)}$'s are generated, the actually transmitted signals are given by $\Pi(t)x^t$'s.

Where each columns $\Pi^{(t)} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t \times N_t}$, and row of only has one nonzero element with the value of one, and Π^t can permute the entries in $X^{\wedge}(t)$. We consider that Π^t 's for $1 \leq t \leq G$ are different in different time slots, and they are predefined and known by both the transmitter and receiver. In this way, the active antennas vary in different time slots from the same transmission group even though $x(t)$'s share the common spatial constellation symbol. Hence, the channel diversity can be appropriately exploited to improve the signal detection at the receiver. In this way, the active antennas vary in different time slots from the same transmission group even though $x(t)$'s share the common spatial constellation symbol. Hence, the channel diversity can be appropriately exploited to improve the signal detection at the receiver.

SCS Based Signal Detector at the Receiver:

At the receiver, the received signal in the t th time slot is where is the DE interleaving processing we observe that $x(t)$'s share the structured sparsity, but they have different non-zero values. According to SCS theory, the structured sparsity of $x(t)$'s can be exploited to improve the signal detection performance compared with the conventional CS based signal detectors. Under the framework of SCS theory, the solution to can be achieved by solving the following optimization problem. This paper has proposed massive SM-MIMO. First, the grouped transmission scheme can introduce the desired structured sparsity of multiple SM signals in the same transmission group for improved signal detection performance. Second, the SSP algorithm can jointly detect multiple SM signals with low complexity. Third, by using SM signal interleaving, by fully exploiting the channel diversity to further improve the signal detection performance, and the gain from SM signal interleaving can approach that of the ideal case of mutually independent channel matrices in the same transmission group. Besides, we have quantified the gain from SM signal interleaving. Simulation results have confirmed the near optimal performance of the proposed scheme. A simulation study was carried out to compare the performance of the proposed SCS-based signal detector with that of the conventional LMMSE-based signal detector and the CS-based signal detector. The performance of the optimal ML detector is also provided as the benchmark for comparison. The proposed SCS-based signal detector outperforms the conventional CS-based signal detector, since the structured sparsity of multiple sparse SM signals is exploited. Moreover, since the channel diversity can be also exploited.

Simulated Output:

Compares the simulated and analytical spatial constellation symbol error rate (SCSER) of the SCS-based signal detector in different cases over uncorrelated rayleigh-fading MIMO channel. Provides SCSER comparison of different signal detectors over correlated Rayleigh-fading MIMO channels, where both the channel correlation coefficients at the transmitter and receiver are 8-PSK are considered. The conventional LMMSE-based signal detector works poorly due to $N_r \ll N_t$. The SCS-based signal detector with interleaving outperforms the conventional CS-based signal detector and SCS-based signal detector without interleaving. Moreover, it has the similar performance with that with mutually independent channel matrices.

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